

ON THE MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF PULTRUDED FIBRE REINFORCED PLATE MATERIAL SUBJECTED TO HYGROTHERMAL AGING

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents experimental findings from characterization work to understand mechanical property changes of a polymeric composite after exposure to hot/wet conditioning. In this work, an ‘off-the-shelf’ pultruded E-glass FRP plate was investigated at the coupon level. 425 specimens cut from the same 6.35 mm thick flat sheet were fully immersed in distilled water at the four constant temperatures of 25, 40, 60 and 80°C, in order to accelerate the moisture kinetics and hydrothermal effects. Batches of five specimens per temperature, an per age of 28, 56, 112 and 224 days, were examined in terms of moisture uptake (mass change) and tested for strength under compressive, in-plane shear and pin-bearing. For compression and pin-bearing testing the loading was aligned to the direction of pultrusion and transverse to this longitudinal direction. The understanding of the relationship between the mechanical property retention and hygrothermal aging is discussed. Knowledge of this relationship can be imperatively employed for categorizing FRP material in terms of their long-term performance in the composite structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

The lack of data to assess the effect of environmental aging on Pultruded Fibre Reinforced Polymer (PFRP) components is recognized to be a crucial barrier to exploitation in civil engineering structures [1]. This weakness manifests itself when designing structures by the need for ‘severe’ knock-down factors to make allowances for material property degradation [2]. FRPs have a property portfolio that make this structural material a candidate to contribute to us achieving sustainable construction, and PFRP thin-walled shapes and systems are known to offer resistance to chemicals [3-4]. One obstacle preventing their exploitation is the lack of long-term durability and performance data.

Characterization of FRPs exposed to aggressive hot/wet conditioning for prolonged periods of time has demonstrated that they can experience significant loss in mechanical properties [5-8] due to internal degradation [9-11]. Environments used by these researchers could realistically be expected when PFRP structures, having service lives of tens of years, are exposed to the vagaries of field environments (e.g. from the weather or from the sea).

This paper presents test results to illustrate the effect of hot-wet conditioning on a number of properties for a PFRP ‘off-the-shelf’ flat sheet material. Knowledge of strength (and stiffness) changes with time will help to develop numerical methods to provide structural analysis outputs that will optimize a FRP structure to meet the specified design requirements in civil engineering works.

In this regard, test coupons for compression, in-plane shear and pin-bearing properties were fully immersed in distilled water at four constant temperatures from 25 to 80°C, and for four aging times up to a maximum of 224 days [12]. Note that 80°C is more than 20°C below [12] the glass transition temperature for the PFRP material.

Moisture absorption measurements on immersed samples were obtained in order to determine the bulk moisture diffusivity by applying Fickian theory [1]. To evaluate the subsequent deterioration of mechanical properties we used batches of five specimens for both aged and un-aged coupons. In addition, to discover whether or not mechanical properties might be dependent on reinforcement

orientation or coupon size the performance these are variable in the test matrix. An understanding of the relationship between property retention and hygrothermal aging will be developed by researchers at the Universities of Glasgow and Newcastle, who are developing a computational approach within the framework of the DURACOMP project (EPSRC - Providing Confidence in Durable Composites). Accompanying tensile properties for the PFRP flat sheet in this study will be reported from collaborative work in the DURACOMP project at Bath University.

2 MATERIAL AND SPECIMENS

425 coupon specimens were cut from a pultruded flat sheet (FS040.101.096A (1/4"×48"×96" /Series 1500 (I))) supplied by Creative Pultrusions Inc. [13]. The nominal thickness is 6.4 mm. It comprises of an isophthalic polyester based matrix and E-glass fibre reinforcement. The lay-up has three Continuous Strand Mat (CSM) layers with a 33.3% fibre volume fraction and two UniDirectional (UD) roving layers having a fibre volume fraction of 54%. These fibre fractions are the averages from a batch of five specimens using the resin burn-off test method. There is a thin veil layer of polyester at the outer surfaces to protect the flat sheet from UV radiation and, also, to retard moisture ingress. The photograph in Fig. 1 shows the structure of the material (three CSM and two UD layers) after the polymer resin had been burnt off. It is worthy to mention that from Fig. 1 it can be seen that, locally, the thickness of the three CSM layers are different, and so are the two UD layers.

Coupons were cut to one of the three different sizes of: 70×50 mm for compression loading; 250×25 mm for 10° off axis coupon and in-plane shear loading; and 80×80 mm (with a 12 mm semi-circular notch at the middle of one of the 80 mm long edges) for pin-bearing loading. Specimens were full immersion in four Grant thermostatic water tanks that were filled with distilled water. The four constant temperatures were 25, 40, 60 and 80°C. Fig. 2 shows a water tank with immersed coupons. For compressive and bearing strengths there were two batches of five specimens for measurement of longitudinal and transverse properties to examine changes with material orientation.

Figure 1. Lay-up construction of the flat sheet PFRP material.

Figure 2. Grant water tank with immersed specimens.

Table 1 details the coupon shapes and sizes. They had been roughly cut-out from the as-received flat sheet using a water-cooled diamond saw, and then CNC machined to give precise plan dimensions. Column (1) in the table introduces the load test and column (2) gives the nominal coupon dimensions. The constant temperatures for the hot/wet aging are listed in column (3). Under the sub-headings of the column the aging time in number of days is given in column (4), and the five rows for each mechanical test define the number of coupons at each temperature and aging interval. For compression and pin-bearing testing the '×2' is because there are specimen batches for the longitudinal and transverse material orientations.

Moisture absorption was measured, according to ASTM D 5229. The relative moisture change ($M(\%)$) for a specimen was determined using:

$$M(\%) = \frac{M_t - M_0}{M_0} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where M_t is the mass at time t and M_0 is the dry mass and $t = 0$ days.

For the moisture diffusion coefficient calculation the second of Fick's laws was employed, assuming uniform moisture and temperature conditions inside the material:

$$\frac{\partial x}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} \quad (2)$$

where x is distance in the thickness direction of the material, C the concentration of the water and D the diffusion coefficient [14].

Sample type (1)	Dimensions (mm) (2)	Aging temperature (°C) (3)	Aging time (days)/No. samples (4)				
			-	28	56	112	224
In-plane shear	250×25	Non-aged	5	-	-	-	-
		25	-	5	5	5	5
		40	-	5	5	5	5
		60	-	5	5	5	5
		80	-	5	5	5	5
Compression	70×50	Non-aged	5×2	-	-	-	-
		25	-	5×2	5×2	5×2	5×2
		40	-	5×2	5×2	5×2	5×2
		60	-	5×2	5×2	5×2	5×2
		80	-	5×2	5×2	5×2	5×2
Bearing	80×80	Non-aged	5×2	-	-	-	-
		25	-	5×2	5×2	5×2	5×2
		40	-	5×2	5×2	5×2	5×2
		60	-	5×2	5×2	5×2	5×2
		80	-	5×2	5×2	5×2	5×2

Table 1. Samples and corresponding aging temperatures/time in days.

Moisture absorption and diffusion processes are functions of temperature, the type of the material, fibre orientation and fibre volume fraction [15-16]. According to information in [14] the one-dimensional solution to Equ. 2 is:

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = 1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2k+1)^2} \exp\left(-\frac{D(2k+1)^2 \pi^2 t}{h^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

Subsequently, Equ. 3 can be simplified for short and long-term approximations, respectively:

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = \frac{4}{\pi^2} \sqrt{\frac{Dt}{h^2}} \quad \text{for } Dt/h^2 < 0.04 \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = 1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \exp\left(\frac{-Dt}{h^2} \pi^2\right) \quad \text{for } Dt/h^2 > 0.04. \quad (5)$$

As long as M_∞ can be determined from the gravimetric curve, the 'Fickian' case being illustrated in Fig. 3, D for a statistically homogeneous gain material can be determined using the following expression and two data points for the moisture gain M_1 and M_2 at times t_1 and t_2 (Fig. 3):

$$D = \pi \left(\frac{h}{4M_\infty}\right)^2 \left(\frac{M_2 - M_1}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}}\right)^2 \left(1 + \frac{h}{l} + \frac{h}{w}\right)^{-2} \quad (6)$$

where l , w , h represent for a specimen the length, width and thickness dimension. For Equ. 6 to be acceptable the moisture diffusion process is assumed to occur mainly in the thickness direction (although it is known that moisture movement along fibres can lead to much higher 'diffusion' in the pultrusion direction). The dimensional parameter of h/w in Equ. 6 is there to account for the contribution to sorption through the edge surfaces of the specimen [17].

Figure 3. Representation of the classical Fickian diffusion curve for $M(t)$ vs. \sqrt{t} [1].

3.2 Mechanical testing

Short-term static tests were conducted at room temperature ($21 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) for un-aged and aged coupons to determine strengths for in-plane shear, compression, and pin-bearing using either an 100 kN Testometric testing machine, or if load was higher an 400 kN Amsler machine. Shown in Figs. 4(a) to 4(c) are the coupon test set-ups. In the pin-bearing test method shown in Fig. 4(c), the ‘pin’ was a FRP rod of the same 12 mm diameter as the semi-circular notch at the middle of the top edge. Strength determination was carried out by applying a constant stroke rate of 0.01 mm/s up to ultimate failure.

For compression and shear loads, the moduli of elasticity were determined, and the results for stiffness changes with time (which are lower) will be reported elsewhere.

Figure 4. Three tests set up used at the University of Warwick for characterizing mechanical properties: a) In-plane shear test; b) Compression test; c) Bearing strength test.

3.2.1 In-plane shear strength

The plan dimensions of the in-plane shear coupon were set at 240×25 mm. Figure 4(a) shows the test set-up with the 100 kN testing machine that subject the coupon to tension loading to determine shear strength, τ_u . The ten-degree (10°) off-axis test method was employed [18]. This non-standard method requires straightforward and economical specimen preparation and needs only a standard tensile testing machine with no special loading fixture. Another advantage is that all the material in the gauge length experiences the same shear deformation. The main weakness with the method is the complexity of the data reduction to determine the in-plane modulus of elasticity. Because the test data is sensitive to the angle between the principal axis of the UD fibres and the tensile loading axis special care is given to the machining of the rectangular coupons and experimental set-up to ensure the orientation is as close as practical to 10° . A shear-loaded coupon had, at its centre and on one surface only, a 5 mm three-element strain gauge rosette. The gauge measured strain in the longitudinal (0°),

and in the 45° and transverse (90°) directions. These three direct strains were continuously monitored using an ORION 3531D Schlumberger data logger and were analyzed [18] using a Matlab code.

3.2.2 Compressive Strength

The plan size for the compression coupon was set at 70×50 mm. Fig. 4(b) shows the University of Warwick in-house test rig that applies concentric compression loading via the 100 kN testing machine. The grip fixture takes a specimen of a nominal width of 50 mm, and at the top and bottom has a 25 mm deep slot to support and clamp the 70 mm long coupon. Further information on this non-standard test method is to be found in reference [19, 20]. It is noteworthy that because the coupons were prepared with precision it can be assumed that there is a uniform compressive stress in the 20 mm gauge length (see Fig. 4(b)). Compression coupons were strain-gauged, at the centre and on the both surfaces, with 6 mm uni-axial gauges to measure longitudinal strain and establish that the difference on the two sides is not > 5% [19]. The direct strains were continuously monitored as per for the in-plane shear tests.

3.2.3 Pin-Bearing Strength

The specimen size was 80×80 mm, and strength testing (no stiffness was measured) was performed with a 'pin' cut from a pultruded FRP rod having nominal diameter of 12 mm. The rod material was pultruded with UD reinforcement and supplied by Exel Composites (UK) Ltd. The diameter of the semi-circular notch in the coupon was precisely drilled and reamed, using CNC machine, to match the size of the rod for having a tight-fit; the clearance was 0.1 to 0.3 mm. With a coupon prior to testing, Fig. 4(c) shows the compression die set for the in-house test method. The pin-bearing strength (F_{θ}^{br} , where subscript θ is for 0° or 90°) was determined by dividing the maximum measured compression force by the projected area (nominally 76.8 mm²), which is given by plate thickness times the rod diameter.

4 TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Figs. 5(a) to 5(d) the mean moisture uptake, as a percentage of the original mass, M_0 are plotted against time (in days). Data points with the symbols of a: green circle; dark blue triangle; brown square; blue rhombus, are, respectively, for the constant aging temperatures of 25, 40, 60 and 80 °C. The $M(t)$ s plotted were calculated using Equ. 1, and are for the mean of five specimens at each temperature/time interval. Because of the substantial mass loss at 80°C, for a non-Fickian response [1], the ordinate scale has a negative part. The initial gradient of the curves represents the rate of moisture sorption; there could be mass loss at all temperatures due to leaching out of low molecular weight species [21].

From the curves in Figs. 5(a) to 5(d) it can be observed that the rate and maximum moisture uptake ($M(\%)$) increases with elevated temperature. The results show that no coupon size at the two temperatures of 25°C (green coloured curves) and 40°C (dark blue curves) had reached the moisture saturation state after 224 days. Coupons immersed at 60°C (brown curves) are found to have reach saturation after approximately 112 days. The equivalent number of days to saturation at 80°C is approximately 16 days for the in-plane coupon size of 250×25 mm and 40 days for the compression size of 70×70 mm size. For all the samples immersed at 80°C, there is a net mass loss after about 110 to 140 days. This is clear evidence for significant material degradation that could be for a degradation mechanism or mechanisms not likely to exist in the field.

Plotted in Figs. 6(a) to 6(d) are curves for mean moisture uptake per constant temperature as a function of \sqrt{t} in days. Both longitudinal (0°) and transverse (90°) direction specimens are included for the compression and bearing coupons. In each figure there are the five curves coloured: green for the 250×25 mm specimens; dark blue for longitudinal of size 70×50 mm; red for the transverse of 70×50 mm; light blue and light brown for the longitudinal and transverse pin-bearing coupons of size 80×80 mm. The filled symbols along the curves are for the mean moisture values. Ignoring the results obtained from the longitudinal bearing specimens, it is observed that the initial rate of moisture uptake

and the maximum moisture is independent of sample size, and thereby the UD reinforcement direction. A reason for this finding could be the small size of the specimens. Edge effects (for moisture diffusion over the four edge surface areas) have a large uptake effect on in relation to diffusion via the other two surfaces in the plane of the material.

Figures 5. Mean moisture uptake curves against the time (days) up to 224 days for three specimen sizes at four different temperatures: (a) 240×25 mm; (b) and (c) 70×50 mm; (d) 80×80 mm.

The resulted presented in the curves in Fig. 6 emphasis, again, that, for the chosen coupon sizes, the rate of moisture absorption increases with elevated soaking temperature from 25°C in Fig. 6(a) to 80°C in Fig. 6(d).

Reported in Table 2 are the results for M_{∞} and D . Presented in column (1) are the sample sizes and the direction for loading for compression, in-plane shear and pin-bearing. Given in the columns (2) is M_{∞} as percentage of M_0 and in column (3) is D based on using Equ. 6. Both properties from the 224 days data are presented with respect to the aging temperatures. Results for D is reported just for two highest temperatures of 60 and 80°C which samples have reached to the maximum moisture content (see Figs. 5 and 6).

Ignoring M_{∞} obtained from the longitudinal bearing specimens at 25°C in column (2) of Table 2, the results for all other sample sizes at each constant temperature are approximately identical. From D s values for two investigated aging temperatures reported in column (3), it can be seen that diffusion coefficient values increase with temperature. This is mainly attributed due to the extra thermal energy that increases the molecular mobility and therefore facilitates the moisture diffusion process.

Presented in Table 3 are test results for mean compressive strength reduction in the longitudinal and transverse directions. This strength is determined as the mean from five specimens in a batch at each temperature/time interval. Strength reductions in percentage (un-aged – aged / un-aged) are

calculated based on the un-aged mean strength, which for compressive strength are 377 N/mm² and 148 N/mm² in the longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively. Using a statistical analysis based on taking the Gaussian distribution, the coefficient of variations (CVs) are 10% and 6%, respectively. The equivalent values for the aged flat sheet are reported in Table 3. For the longitudinal situation they are between 4% and 18% and for the transverse direction they are 2% to 11%.

Figure 6. Mean moisture uptake curves against time (\sqrt{t}) for the three specimen sizes of 240×25 mm for in-plane shear, 70×50 mm for compression and 80×80 mm for pin-bearing for up to 224 days: (a) 25°C; (b) 40°C; (c) 60°C; (d) 80°C.

Specimen size (mm)	M_{∞} (%)				D ($\times 10^{-6}$ mm ² /s)	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	25°C	40°C	60°C	80°C	60°C	80°C
70×50×6.4 (0°)	1.14	1.50	1.84	1.75	2.9	11.0
70×50×6.4 (90°)	1.22	1.52	1.67	1.70	2.7	11.1
250×25×6.4	1.26	1.59	1.51	1.69	2.9	8.8
80×80×6.4(0°)	1.73	1.64	1.75	1.79	3.5	6.6
80×80×6.4(90°)	1.20	1.55	1.69	1.76	3.6	3.9

Table 2. Maximum moisture uptake and diffusion coefficients.

Strength reductions reported in Table 3 confirm that deterioration in strength is occurring, under almost all environmental conditionings. This reduction in the longitudinal is between 1% for 25°C/112 days aging and 44% for 80°C/224. The equivalent values in the transverse direction are in the range of 11% and 66% for 40°C/28 and 80°C/224 days, respectively. For transverse direction, it is observed that compressive strength was increased by 1% for 25°C/28 and 25°C/56 days conditioning.

In addition, at 80°C and 224 days for the same mass increase of about 1.7% the strength reduction in transvers direction is 1.5 times greater than in longitudinal direction.

Time (days)	28	56	112	224	28	56	112	224
	Mean longitudinal (0°) compressive strength reduction %				Mean transverse (90°) compressive strength reduction %			
Temperature								
25°C	2	0	1	6	+1	+1	18	17
40°C	6	4	11	10	11	16	24	30
60°C	6	22	8	26	26	32	37	40
80°C	5	25	27	44	41	48	61	66

Table 3. Compressive strength reductions in the longitudinal and transverse directions.

Mean strength reduction, in percentage, from in-plane shear tests for hot/wet aging coupons are reported in Table 4. Reductions values are determined based on 34.5 N/mm² for un-aged batch with CV of 2%. For all aged batches CV was between 2% to 11%. The same as the results given in Table 3 from compression tests, strength deterioration for in-plane shear is elevated with hygrothermal aging. It is noticeable that strength degradation of the material is fully recovered for the batch aged at 60°C/28 days. The 80°C/224 batch has the maximum strength reduction and that is about 48%.

Time (days)	28	56	112	224
	Mean in-plane shear strength reduction %			
Temperature				
25°C	8	3	10	13
40°C	8	3	13	15
60°C	1	12	14	24
80°C	8	22	28	48

Table 4. Test results for in-plane shear strength with hot/wet aging.

Strength reduction results in percentage reported in Table 5 are from the pin-bearing series of tests. As expected from the characterization of compression and in-plane strengths in Tables 3 and 4, this connection strength reduces with increase temperature and/or time of aging. To establish mean pin-bearing strength reductions following hot/wet aging the un-aged mean strengths are 304 N/mm² and 213 N/mm² in the longitudinal and transverse directions. These means have a CV of 3 and 5%. The longitudinal strengths reported in Table 5 have CVs between 2 and 14% and transverse strengths from 3 to 24%.

As for the compression and in-plane strengths reported in Tables 3 and 4, the hygrothermal aging at 80°C induced the most significant reductions in pin-bearing strength. This strength reduction in longitudinal and transverse directions is 40 and 48%. After 224 days for the same mass increase of about 1.8% the strength reduction in the 90° direction is found to be 1.4 times greater than in the 0° direction. As seen in Table 5 the strength reduction is recovered for the batch of specimens in longitudinal direction aged at 60°C temperature and additional post-curing occurs which exceeds the effect of material degradation aged at 40°C.

Time (days)	28	56	112	224	28	56	112	224
	Mean longitudinal bearing strength reduction %				Mean transverse bearing strength reduction %			
Temperature								
25°C	0	7	10	8	4	10	8	3
40°C	12	13	13	20	+1	4	16	20
60°C	6	9	11	17	10	23	22	31
80°C	12	18	31	40	26	24	38	56

Table 5. Test results for bearing strength reduction in the longitudinal and transverse directions with hot/wet aging.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, 425 specimens were subjected to hot/wet aging comprising of the four constant temperatures of 25, 40, 60 and 80°C and a number of days to a maximum of 224 day. For the pultruded FRP flat sheet characterized it was observed that, with temperature increase, there is an increase in moisture uptake rate, the maximum moisture uptake, the time to when the maximum occurs and the diffusion coefficient. Furthermore, hygrothermal aging at 80°C induces significant reductions in the strengths for compressive, in-plane shear and pin-bearing loadings. Moreover, at 80°C, and for the same mass increase of about 1.7% after 224 days, the compression and pin-bearing strength reductions in the transverse direction are 1.4-1.5 times greater than in longitudinal direction. For the longitudinal batch aged at 60°C it was found that the pin-bearing strength reduction showed a recovery after 28, 56, 112 and 224 days and this could be due to post-curing have a beneficial effect on strength that exceeds the reduction due to any material degradation. At 40°C there is degradation and maybe no post-curing enhancement. The results reported for hot/wet aging at the four constant temperatures indicate that the initial rate of moisture uptake and the maximum moisture uptake are independent of sample size and orientation of the unidirectional rovings with respect to the loading direction in the compression and pin-bearing series of tests. A reason for this finding could be the small size of the specimens. Edge effects (for moisture diffusion over the four edge surface areas) have a large uptake effect on in relation to diffusion via the other two surfaces in the plane of the material.

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REFERENCES

- [1] V.M. Karbhari, (Ed.), *Durability of composites for civil structural applications*, Woodhead Pub., Cambridge, UK (& CRC Press, Boca Raton), 2007.
- [2] B. Zafari, *Startlink building system and connections for fibre reinforced polymer structures*, PhD thesis, The University of Warwick, UK, 2012.
- [3] Anonymous, *The new and improved Pultrex® pultrusion design manual (Imperial version)*, Creative Pultrusions, Inc., Alum Bank, PA. (www.creativepultrusions.com/rd.html) (May 20, 2015).
- [4] Anonymous *Strongwell design manual*, Strongwell, Bristol, Va. (www.strongwell.com/) (June 8, 2015).
- [5] A. Apicella, C. Migliaresi, L. Nicolais, L. Iaccarino and S. Roccotelli S. The water ageing of unsaturated polyester-based composites: Influence of resin chemical structure, *Composites*, 14 4, 1983, 387-392.
- [6] W.L. Bradley and T.S. Grant, The effect of moisture absorption on the interfacial strength of polymeric matrix composites, *Material Science*, 30 21, 1985, 5537-5542.
- [7] S. Sridharan, A-H. Zureick and J.D. Muzzy, Effect of hot-wet environments on E-glass/vinylester composites *Proceedings of the 56th Annual Technical Conference of the Society of Plastics Engineers*, 1998, 2255-2259.
- [8] S.P. Phifer, K.N.E. Verghese and J.J. Lesko, Remaining strength of hygrothermally aged pultruded vinylester E-glass composites, *Proceedings of 3rd International Conference on Advanced Composite Materials in Bridges and Structures*, Ottawa, Canada, 2000, 29-36.
- [9] I. Ghorbel and D.Valentin, Hydrothermal effects on the physico-chemical properties of pure and glass fiber reinforced polyester and vinylester resins, *Polymer Composites*, 14 4, 1993, 324-334.

- [10] J.W. Chin, T. Nguyen and K. Aouadi, Effects of environmental exposure on fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) materials used in construction, *Journal of Composites Technology*, **19**(4), 1997, 205-213.
- [11] Barker K, *Review of Housing Supply*. Final Report- Recommendations. The Office of the Deputy Prime Minister, London, 2004, UK.
- [12] L.C Bank, T.R. Gentry, B.J. Thompson and J.S. Russell, A model specification for FRP composites for civil engineering structures, *Construction and Building Materials*, **17**, 2003, pp. 405-437.
- [14] J. Crank, *The mathematics of diffusion*, Oxford University Press, UK, 1975.
- [15] R.M.V.G.K. Rao, N. Balasubramanian, and M. Chanda, Factors Affecting Moisture Absorption in Polymer Composites Part I: Influence of Internal Factors, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **3**, 1984, pp. 232-245.
- [16] R.M.V.G.K. Rao, M. Chanda, N. Balasubramanian, Factors Affecting Moisture Absorption in Polymer Composites Part II: Influence of External Factors, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **3**, 1984, pp. 246-253.
- [17] C.-H. Shen and G.S. Springer, Moisture absorption and desorption of composite materials, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **10**, 1976, pp. 2-20.
- [18] CC Chamis, JH Sinclair, Ten-degree off-axis test for shear properties in fibre composites, *Exp. Mech.*, **17**, 1977, pp. 339–346.
- [19] J.T. Mottram, Compression strength of pultruded flat sheet material, *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, **62**, 1994, pp. 185-200.
- [20] J.T. Mottram, and B. Zafari, Pin-bearing strengths for design of bolted connections in pultruded structures, *Structures and Buildings*, 164 Issue SB5, 2011, pp. 291-305..
- [21] T. Morii, T. Tanimoto, H. Hamada, Z.-I. Maekawa, T. Hirano, K. Kiyosumi, Weight changes of a randomly orientated GRP panel in hot water, *Composites Science and Technology*, **49**, 1993, 209-216.